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ZIGBEE: A LOW POWER WIRELESS TECHNOLOGY FOR INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT:

The great potential of Wireless Sensor Network is being seen in industrial, consumer and commercial application. The wireless technology is becoming one of the most prominent areas of research. This paper focuses on the most widely used transceiver standard in Wireless Sensor Networks, a ZigBee technology. ZigBee over IEEE 802.15.4 defines specifications for low data rate WPAN (LR-WPAN) to support low power monitoring and controlling devices. This paper presents a Zigbee wireless standard, IEEE 802.15.4specification, ZigBee device types, the protocol stack architecture and its applications.

KEYWORDS:

ZigBee, IEEE802.15.4

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REFERENCES

- [1] ZigBee Alliance, ZigBee Specification[z]. Version 1.0, <http://www.ZigBee.org>, 2005-06-27
- [2] ShizhuangLin; JingyuLiu; YanjunFang; Wuhan Univ., Wuhan" [ZigBee Based Wireless Sensor Networks and Its Applications in Industrial](#)"IEEE International Conference on Automation and Logistics, 200718-21Aug.2007page(s):1979-1983Location:Jinan
- [3] Zhou Yiming, Yang Xianglong, Guo Xishan, Zhou Mingang, Wang Liren ,” A Design of Greenhouse Monitoring & Control System Based on ZigBee Wireless Sensor Network”,IEEE journal-4244-1312-5/07 2007
- [4] R Vishnubhotla, PS Rao, A Ladha, S Kadiyala, A Narmada, B Ronanki, S Illapakurthi,”[ZigBee Based Multi-Level Parking Vacancy Monitoring System](#)” 978-1-4244-6875-10/2010 IEEE pg 2563-2566
- [5] Xiuping Zhang; Guangjie Han; Changping Zhu; Yan Dou; Jianfeng Tao;” [Research of Wireless Sensor Networks based on ZigBee for Miner Position](#)”, [J] International Symposium on Computer, Communication, Control and Automation, IEEE. 29 July 2010Pg1 – 5
- [6] Dunfan Ye, Daoli Gong, Wei Wang,“Application of Wireless Sensor Networks in Environmental Monitoring”2nd International Conference on Power Electronics and Intelligent Transportation SystemIEEE2009pg 2563-2567
- [7] ShizhuangLin; JingyuLiu; YanjunFang; Wuhan Univ.,Wuhan” [ZigBee Based Wireless Sensor Networks and Its Applications in Industrial](#)” ,IEEE International Conference on Automation and Logistics18-21Aug.2007Pg1979-1983

A Time Series ANN Approach for Weather Forecasting

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Abstract:

Weather forecasting is most challenging problem around the world. There are various reason because of its experimented values in meteorology, but it is also a typical unbiased time series forecasting problem in scientific research. A lots of methods proposed by various scientists. The motive behind research is to predict more accurate. This paper contribute the same using artificial neural network (ANN) and simulated in MATLAB to predict two important weather parameters i.e. maximum and minimum temperature. The model has been trained using past 60 years of real data collected from(1901-1960) and tested over 40 years to forecast maximum and minimum temperature. The results based on mean square error function (MSE) confirm, this model which is based on multilayer perceptron has the potential to successful application to weather forecasting.

Keywords:

Artificial neural network, Multilayer perceptron, Time series analysis, Mean Square error function, MATLAB.

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REFERENCES:

1. Paras, S.Mathur, A.Kumar and M.Chandra (2007), "[A Feature Based Neural Network Model for Weather Forecasting](#)",World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology.
2. Mr.R.C vashishtha, director IMD.
3. S N Sivanandam, S Sumathi, S N Deepa, "Introduction to neural Networks using MATLAB".
4. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Neural_network.
5. Rosenblatt, Frank. x.(1961),"Principles of Neurodynamics: Perceptrons and the Theory of Brain Mechanisms", Spartan Books, Washington DC.
6. Rumelhart, David E., Geoffrey E. Hinton, and R. J. Williams (1986),"[Learning Internal Representations by Error Propagation](#)". David E. Rumelhart, James L. McClelland, and the PDP research group. (editors), Parallel distributed processing: Explorations in the microstructure of cognition, Volume 1: Foundations. MIT Press.
7. Cybenko, G. (1989), "Approximation by superpositions of a sigmoidal function Mathematics of control, Signals, and Systems (MCSS)", 2(4), 303–314.
8. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Multilayer_perceptron.
9. Ramasubramanian V."Time Series Analysis", I.A.S.R.I,Library Avenue,New Delhi.
10. <http://www.tropmet.res.in>.
11. <http://www.imd.gov.in>.
12. Chattopadhyay S. (2006), "Multilayered feed forward Artificial Neural Network model to predict the average summer-monsoon rainfall in India",IEEE ,Vol.:11, pp.:125-130
13. Zan C. (2009) "Myanmar Rainfall Forecasting Using Hidden Markov Model",IEEE International Advance Computing Conference.
14. Hayati M. and Mohebi Z.(2007) , "[Temperature Forecasting Based on neural Network Approach](#)", World Applied Sciences Journal 2 (6):613-620.ISSN 1818-4952.

TAKAGI-SUGENO MODEL FOR QUADROTOR MODELLING AND CONTROL USING NONLINEAR STATE FEEDBACK CONTROLLER

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we present a Takagi-Sugeno (T-S) model for Quadrotor modelling. This model is developed using multiple model approach, composed of three locally accurate models valid in different region of the operating space. It enables us to model the global nonlinear system with some degree of accuracy. Once the T-S model has been defined it is claimed to be relatively straightforward to design a controller with the same strategy of T-S model. A nonlinear state feedback controller based on Linear Matrix Inequality (LMI), and PDC technique with pole placement constraint is synthesized. The requirements of stability and poleplacement in LMI region are formulated based on the Lyapunov direct method. By recasting these constraints into LMIs, we formulate an LMI feasibility problem for the design of the nonlinear state feedback controller. This controller is applied to a nonlinear Quadrotor system, which is one of the most complex flying systems that exist. A comparative study between controller with stability constraints and controller with pole placement constrains is made. Simulation results show that the controller with pole placement constrains yields good tracking performance. The designed T-S model is validated using Matlab Simulink.

KEYWORDS

Linear Matrix Inequality (LMI), Multiple Model Approach (MMA), Parallel Disturbance Compensation (PDC), Pole Placement, Quadrotor, Takagi-Sugeno model.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Novák. (2007) "linear system identification and control using local model networks". Doctorat Thesis, Faculty of Applied Informatics, Tomas Bata University, Zlín.
- [2] T. Takagi & M. Sugeno, (1985) "Fuzzy identification of systems and its applications to model and control", IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, vol. 15, pp. 116–132.
- [3] H. O. Wang, K. Tanaka, & M. Griffin, (1996) "An approach to fuzzy control of non linear systems : stability and design issues," IEEE Transaction on fuzzy system, vol. 4, pp. 14-23.
- [4] K. Tanaka, . T. Ikeda, & Y. Y. He, (1998) "Fuzzy regulators and fuzzy observers : relaxed stability conditions and LMI-based design," IEEE Transaction on fuzzy system, vol. 6, pp. 250-256.
- [5] S. Boyd, L. El Ghaoui, E. Feron, & V. Balakrishnan (1994) "[Linear Matrix Inequalities in System and Control Theory](#)," SIAM, Philadelphia, USA.
- [6] T. Madani & A. Benallegue, (2006) "Backstepping Sliding Mode Control Applied to a Miniature Quadrotor Flying Robot", IEEE Conference on Industrial Electronics, pp. 700-705.
- [7] Y. Yu, J. Changhong, & W. Haiwei, (2010) "[Backstepping control of each channel for a quadrotor aerial robot](#)", International Conference on Computer, Macaronis, Control and Electronic Engineering (CMCE), pp. 403-407.
- [8] S. Bouabdallah, A. Noth, & R. Siegwart, (2004) "PID vs LQ control techniques applied to an indoor micro quadrotor", IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems, Sendai, Japan, pp. 2451-2456.
- [9] K. Alexis, G. Nikolakopoulos, & A. Tzes, (2010) "Constrained-control of a quadrotor helicopter for trajectory tracking under wind-gust disturbances", IEEE Mediterranean Electro-technical Conference (MELECON), pp. 1411-1416.
- [10] H .Bouadi, S. S. Cunha, A. Drouin, & F. M. Camino, (2011) "Adaptive Sliding Mode Control for Quadrotor Attitude Stabilization and Altitude Tracking", IEEE International Symposium on Computational Intelligence and Informatics, pp. 449-455.
- [11] R. Gao & A. O'Dwyer, (2002) "[Multiple model networks in non-linear system modelling for control—a review](#)", in the 3rd Wismar Automates rungs symposium, Wismar, Germany.
- [12] F. Yacef & F. Boudjema, (2011) "[Local Model Network for non linear modelling and control of an UAV Quadrotor](#)" ", International Conference on Automatic and Macaronis (CIAM), Oran, Algeria, pp. 247-252.

ROBUST SECOND ORDER SLIDING MODE CONTROL FOR A QUADROTOR CONSIDERING MOTOR DYNAMICS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a robust second order sliding mode control (SMC) for controlling a quadrotor with uncertain parameters presented based on high order sliding mode control (HOSMC). A controller based on the HOSMC technique is designed for trajectory tracking of a quadrotor helicopter with considering motor dynamics. The main subsystems of quadrotor (i.e. position and attitude) stabilized using HOSMC method. The performance and effectiveness of the proposed controller are tested in a simulation study taking into account external disturbances with consider to motor dynamics. Simulation results show that the proposed controller eliminates the disturbance effect on the position and attitude subsystems efficiency that can be used in real time applications.

KEYWORDS

Quadrotor, High order sliding mode, Motor dynamics

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Bouabdallah, P. Murriero and R. Siegwart, (2004) "Design and control of an indoor micro quadrotor," IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA '04), Vol.5, pp. 4393 - 4398.
- [2] P. Pounds, R. Mahony and P. Corke, (2006) "[Modelling and Control of a Quad-Rotor Robot](#)," In the Proceedings of the Australasian Conference on Robotics and Automation.
- [3] O. Fritsch, P. De Monte, M. Buhl and B. Lohmann, (2012) "[Quasi-static feedback linearization for the translational dynamics of a quadrotor helicopter](#)," American Control Conference (ACC), 2012, pp. 125 – 130.
- [4] A. A. Mian and W. Daobo, (2008) "[Modelling and Backstepping-based Nonlinear Control Strategy for a 6 DOF Quadrotor Helicopter](#)," Chinese Journal of Aeronautics, Volume 21, Issue 3, pp. 261– 268.
- [5] A. Das, F. Lewis and K. Subbarao, (2009) "[Backstepping Approach for Controlling a Quadrotor Using Lagrange Form Dynamics](#)," Journal of Intelligent and Robotic Systems, Volume 56, Issue 1-2, pp. 127-151.
- [6] R. Zhang, X. Wang and K. Y. Cai, (2009) "Quadrotor aircraft control without velocity measurements," IEEE Conference on Decision and Control, pp. 5213 – 5218.
- [7] Y. Morel and A. Leonessa, (2006) "[Direct Adaptive Tracking Control of Quadrotor Aerial Vehicles](#)," ASME International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition. American Society of Mechanical Engineers, pp. 155-161.
- [8] H. Haomiao, G. M. Hoffmann, S. L. Waslander, and C. J. Tomlin, (2009) "Aerodynamics and control of autonomous quadrotor helicopters in aggressive maneuvering," IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation, ICRA'09, pp. 3277-3282.
- [9] R. Guilherme, V. Manuel, G. Ortega and F. R. Rubio, (2010) "[An integral predictive/nonlinear \$H_\infty\$ control structure for a quadrotor helicopter](#)," Automatica, no. 1, pp. 29-39.
- [10] L. Fridman, A. Poznyak and F. J. Bejarano, (2004) "[Decomposition of the Mini-Max Multimodel Optimal Problem via Integral Sliding Mode Control](#)," Proceedings of the American Control Conference, vol.1, pp. 620 – 625.
- [11] L. Luque-Vega, B. Castillo-Toledo, Alexander G. Loukianov, (2012) "[Robust block second order sliding mode control for a quadrotor](#)," Journal of the Franklin Institute 349, pp. 719–739.

- [12] A. Mokhtari and A. Benallegue, (2003) "[Dynamic feedback controller of Euler angles and wind parameters estimation for a quadrotor unmanned aerial vehicle](#)," American Control Conference (ACC'03), Denver, June.
- [13] A. G. Loukianov, (2002) "[Robust block decomposition sliding mode control design](#)," International Journal Mathematical Problems in Engineering: Theory, Methods and Applications, pp. 349–365.
- [14] S. Mondal, C. Mahanta, (2013) "[Adaptive integral higher order sliding mode controller for uncertain systems](#)," Journal of Control Theory and Applications, Volume 11, Issue 1, pp. 61-68.
- [15] Y. B. Shtessel, I. A. Shkolnikov and M. D. J. Brown, (2003) "[An asymptotic second-order smooth sliding mode control](#)," Asian Journal of Control, pp. 498–504.
- [16] L. Derafa, L. Fridman, A. Benallegue and A. Ouldali, (2010) "[Super twisting control algorithm for the four rotors helicopter attitude tracking problem](#)," In Proceedings of 11th International Workshop on Variable Structure Systems (VSS) Workshop.
- [17] S. Bouabdallah and R. Siegwart, (2005) "Backstepping and sliding-mode techniques applied to an indoor micro quadrotor," In Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA '05), pp. 2247–2252.
- [18] L. Fridman and A. Levant, (1996) "[Sliding Modes of Higher Order as A Natural Phenomenon in Control Theory](#)," In Garofalo F., Glielmo L. (Eds.) Robust Control via Variable Structure and Lyapunov Techniques, Lecture Notes in Control and Information Sciences 217, Springer Verlag, pp. 107-133.
- [19] J. P. Ostrowski and C. J. Taylor, (2005) "[Control of a quadrotor helicopter using dual camera visual feedback](#)," International Journal of Robotics Research, Vol. 24, No. 5, pp. 329-341.
- [20] S. Bouabdallah and R. Siegwart, (2005) "Backstepping and sliding-mode techniques applied to an indoor micro quadrotor," In Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation, pp. 2259-2264.
- [21] H. Bolandi, M. Rezaei, R. Mohsenipour, H. Nemati, S. M. Smailzadeh, (2013) "[Attitude Control of a Quadrotor with Optimized PID Controller](#)," Intelligent Control and Automation, Vol.4, No.3, pp. 335- 342.
- [22] Tommaso Bresciani, (2008) "[Modelling, Identification and Control of a Quadrotor Helicopter](#)," Master Thesis, Department of Automatic Control, Lund University.

- [23] M. Wierema, (2008) “[Design, implementation and flight test of indoor navigation and control system for a quadrotor UAV](#),” Master Thesis, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology.
- [24] D. A. Mercado¹, R. Castro¹ and R. Lozano, (2013) “[Quadrotors Flight Formation Control Using a Leader-Follower Approach](#),” European Control Conference (ECC July 17-19, 2013, Zurich, Switzerland), pp. 3858-3863.
- [25] Hassan K. Khalil, (2002) “Nonlinear Systems,3rd Edition, Prentice Hall, ISBN 0-13-067389-7.
- [26] R. Xu and U. Ozguner, (2006) “[Sliding Mode Control of a Quadrotor Helicopter](#),” Proceedings of the 45th IEEE Conference on Decision & Control, San Diego, CA, USA, pp. 4957- 4962.

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AN EFFICIENT IMPLEMENTATION FOR KEY MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUE USING SMART CARD AND ECIES CRYPTOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

A Elliptic curve cryptosystem are become popular because of the reduced number of keys bits required in Comparision to other cryptosystem. In existing work ECC technique are used to describe the encryption data to provide a security over a network. ECC satisfy the Smart cards requirements in term of memory, processing and cost. In existing work ECC cryptographic Algorithm work with a smart card technique. Many existing approaches work with smart card with various Technique and produce a better efficient result. In these review paper, we Define a smart card technique using a ECIES cryptographic algorithm. So These Technique key management using smart card and ECIES.ECC basically based on a discrete logarithm over appoint on an elliptic curve. The ECIES is standard elliptic curve that is totally based on encryption algorithm. Smart Card using ECIES technique in key management technique.

KEYWORDS

ECIES, elliptic curve, encryption, Decryption, public key cryptography, Smart card, java card.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Swarn Sanjay Sonwanshi,Ram ratan ahirwal,Yogendra kumar jain”An efficient smart card based remote user authentication scheme using hash function”,IEEE ,conferences on electrical,electronics and computer science,2012.
- [2] Patrick george “[user authentication with smart card in trusted computing architecture](#)”Gemplus.
- [3] A.k.awasthi and S.lal,”A remote user authentication scheme using smart card with forward security”,IEEE transactions on consumer Electronics,Vol.49,.no.4,pp,1246-1248,2003.
- [4] B.Baker “[Mutual Authentication with smart card](#)”Delft university of technology,Chicago,Illinois,USA,may 10-11-1999.
- [5] R. ramasamy and Amutha prabakar Muniyandi”[An efficient password authentication scheme for smart card](#)”,international journal of network security ,vol.14,no.3,pp 180-186,may 2012.
- [6] R. ramasamy and Amutha prabakar Muniyandi ”[new remote Mutual Authentication scheme using smart card](#)” transaction on data Privacy 2(2009) 141-152.
- [7] C. K. Chan and L. M. Cheng, “Cryptanalysis of a remote user authentication scheme using smart cards,” IEEE Trans. Consumer Electron., vol. 46, pp. 992-993, 2000.
- [8] C. C. Chang and S. J. Hwang, “[Using smart cards to authenticate remote passwords,](#)” Computers and athematics with applications, vol. 26, No.7, pp. 19-27, 1993.
- [9] C. C. Chang and K. F. Hwang, “[Some forgery attack on a remote user authentication scheme using smart cards,](#)” Infomatics, vol. 14, no. 3, pp.189 - 294, 2003.
- [10] C. C. Chang and T. C. Wu, “[Remote password authentication with smart cards,](#)” IEE Proceedings-E, vol. 138, no. 3, pp. 165-168, 1993.

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